

MAGNETO-CHEMICAL STUDIES IN VALENCY AND MOLECULAR CONSTITUTION. PART I. ISOPOLYMOLYBDATES

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The formation and the composition of isopolymolybdates have been studied by measuring the magnetic susceptibilities of solutions of normal sodium molybdate in aqueous nitric acid of progressively increasing concentration. The susceptibility— p_H curve shows strong deviation from the mixture law and is characterised by having four well-defined inflexion points or breaks, corresponding to the addition of about 4, 7, 9 and 10.5 H-ions for every 6 MoO₄-ions. Formation of *di*-, *para*-, *meta*- and *octo*-molybdates with compositions, as advocated by Jander and co-workers, is thereby confirmed.

The composition and the constitution of the isopoly-acids had been a vexed and complex problem in inorganic chemistry for a long time. Copeaux and Rosenheim extended Miolati's scheme of formulation of the heteropoly-acids, based on Werner's theory, to the case of isopoly-acids (*cf.* Rosenheim, Abegg's Handbuch, Vol IV, Part I, *ii*, pp. 977-1065, 1921). Subsequent investigations by means of various physical methods have led to a more or less complete elucidation of the problem and placed our knowledge of the subject on a much surer footing. The work of Jander and his co-workers has mainly contributed to this end. The methods deal with the study of the aggregation and degradation processes involved in the formation of these poly-acids. The case of isopolymolybdates, with which the present work is concerned, was studied by these workers from a measurement of the rate of diffusion of the polyacid anions formed in solutions of normal sodium molybdate, acidified with nitric acid to progressively increasing H-ion concentrations and containing a large excess of an inert electrolyte (NaNO₃). The ionic weights were determined from the observed diffusion coefficients. The results were confirmed by conductometric titration of a solution of normal sodium molybdate with nitric acid. A study of the absorption spectra of progressively acidified solutions of normal molybdate and the thermometric titration of an alkaline or acidified molybdate solution with acid or alkali, as the case may be, furnished additional support to the results derived from the diffusion method (*cf.* Jander, Jahr and Heukeschoven, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, **194**, 383). The conclusions arrived at by Jander may be summarised as follows:

Normal molybdate		[MoO ₄] ²⁻	...	Stable between	p_H	14-6.5
Dimolybdate		[Mo ₂ O ₁₁] ⁴⁻	...	,, ,,	p_H	6.3-4.5
Paramolybdate		[HMo ₆ O ₂₁] ⁶⁻	...	,, ,,	p_H	4.5-2.9
Trimolybdate		[H ₂ Mo ₆ O ₂₁] ⁴⁻	...	,, ,,	} p_H	2.9-1.5
Metamolybdate		[H ₃ Mo ₆ O ₂₁] ³⁻	...	,, ,,		
Octomolybdate		[H ₇ Mo ₁₂ O ₄₁] ³⁻	...	,, at about	p_H	1.25

The conductometric titration curve similarly reveals discontinuities corresponding to the addition of 4, 7, 9 and 10.5 H-ions for each 6 MoO₄-ions, originally present in the solution. This indicates the formation of *di*-, *para*-, *meta*- and *octo*molybdates respectively.

From potentiometric titration of a solution of molybdic acid with KOH, Travers and Malaparade (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1926, **39**, 1406) obtained evidence for the formation of normal and metamolybdates only.

Britton and German (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2154) also carried out potentiometric and conductometric titrations of a solution of normal sodium molybdate with hydrochloric and

other acids, and obtained inflexions on the titration curves corresponding to para-, tri-, meta- and a higher molybdate.

FIG. I

From conductometric titrations of molybdic acid and sodium molybdate Bye (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1939, 6, 174), however, could detect the formation of only normal and metamolybdates in solution.

Brintzinger and Ratanart (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1935, 224, 97), on the other hand, from a measurement of the rate of electro dialysis of ions in acidified molybdate solutions confirmed Jander's results except in the case of his trimolybdate ion, $(\text{Mo}_3\text{O}_{11})^{4-}$, from a solution of which the dimolybdate crystallises.

In view of this disagreement among different workers about the existence of various polymolybdate ions, it was considered desirable to study the process of aggregation by a new physical method. We have therefore determined the variation of magnetic susceptibility of a solution of normal sodium molybdate, progressively acidified with nitric acid. Every break in the susceptibility— p_H curve indicates deviation from the mixture law and hence points to the formation of a new aggregate in solution, whose composition can be deduced from the difference in the p_H values of the original acid solution and that of the mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure recrystallised normal sodium molybdate, $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and solutions of chemically pure nitric acid of varying strength from about 1N to 0.1N were used in these experiments. Sodium molybdate (1g.) was added to every 25 c.c. of the acid solution of any given strength and the mixtures containing the dissolved salt were weighed (Table I). Magnetic susceptibilities of both the individual acid solutions as well as of the mixtures with dissolved sodium molybdate were determined by Guoy's method. The description of the magnetic balance

has been given in a previous paper (Ráy and Ghose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 323). Susceptibility of the normal sodium molybdate was also determined in order to calculate the values for the mixture law.

Mass susceptibility (χ_g) corrected for air in each case was calculated from the following formula,

$$\chi_g = \frac{2l \times m'}{m \times H^2 \times 1.019} + \chi_v^r / d_s$$

The symbols represent values as stated in previous papers. d_s was obtained from the ratio of the weights of water and the solution concerned, occupying the same volume in the measurement tube.

$$l = 11.4 \text{ cm.}, H = 10.4 \times 10^3 \text{ gauss.}$$

Table I gives the weights of the mixtures containing 1g. of dissolved $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in acid solutions of different strength, as well as in pure water.

TABLE I.

Normality of HNO_3 -solution	...	0.97	0.44	0.33	0.26	0.20	0.18	0.10
Wt. of the salt + acid solution in g	...	25.61	25.13	25.09	25.09	25.05	25.05	25.05
Wt. of the salt + water in g. = 25.05.								

TABLE II

Strength, wt. & D_4^{25} of acid sol.	Pull (-mg.)	$\chi_g \times 10^6$ (neg.)	Wt. & D_4^{25} (salt + acid sol.)	Pull (-mg.)	P_H of the mixture	$\chi_g \times 10^6$ (mixture) neg.	H-ions added per 6MoO_4^{--} from col. 1 & 6.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$ mixture law (neg.)
0.97 N	—	—	4.3019 g. ($D=1.07$)	14.0	<< 1	0.647	—	—
0.44 N 4.1150 g. $D=1.027$	13.9	0.671	4.2130 g. $D=1.057$	14.2	1.2	0.671	—	0.652
0.33 N	—	0.677	4.2150 g. $D=1.055$	14.5	1.5	0.686	10.83	0.658
0.26 N	—	0.683	4.200 g. $D=1.054$	14.4	3.0	0.683	9.4	0.663
0.20 N	—	0.687	4.204 g. $D=1.053$	14.0	4.7	0.663	7.26	0.667
0.18 N 4.099 g. $D=1.023$	14.2	0.688	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.10 N 3.6868 g. $D=1.002$	13.0	0.702	4.203 g. $D=1.051$	14.0	6.0	0.663	3.63	0.681
Salt solution in water	—	—	4.1749 g. $D=1.047$	14.2	7.4	0.677	—	0.699

The standard value of -0.72×10^{-6} was taken for the mass susceptibility of water. The susceptibility data recorded in the above table represent reproducible values of two independent series of measurements.

The results of measurements are summarised in Table II.

The mass susceptibility for $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was measured and corrected for air $\chi_g = 0.189 \times 10^{-6}$. From this and that of the acid solution in each case χ_g values for the mixtures employed were calculated on the basis of mixture law according to the formula:—

χ_g (mix.) = $x \chi_g$ (salt) + $(1-x) \chi_g$ (acid); where x = wt. in gram of $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in one gram weight of the mixture. The values are given in the appropriate column of Table II.

χ_g values for some of the acid solutions were directly measured, while those for others were calculated by interpolation. p_n values for the mixtures were measured in all cases excepting for 0.97N by means of glass electrodes. The value for the last named was determined by the indicator method.

DISCUSSION

Since the progressive aggregation of MoO_4 -ion occurs through the addition of H-ions, which leads to the formation of various isopolymolybdates, the number of H-ions thus removed by interaction with MoO_4 gives an idea of the composition of the aggregates formed. In Table II are shown the number of H-ions thus removed in different cases for every 6 MoO_4 -ions. On plotting the mass susceptibility values for various mixtures against the corresponding p_n values and also against the normality of the original acid solutions employed for making the mixtures, the curve I, as shown in the Fig 1, is obtained. It shows distinct breaks or inflexions at points corresponding to certain p_n values of the mixtures. These points of discontinuity in the susceptibility p_n curve at p_n values of 6, 4.7, 3 and 1.5 are found on calculation to correspond to the interaction with 3.6, 7.3, 9.4 and 10.8 H-ions respectively for every 6 MoO_4 -ions of the normal molybdate used. This is in good agreement with the results of conductivity titration and confirms Jander's results of diffusion experiments regarding the composition of isopolymolybdates in solution. This is evident from the following representation of the aggregation process that occurs at these transition points.

These represent respectively the di-, para-, meta- and octomolybdates of the older classification. No indication of the formation of the trimolybdate could be detected between the para- and meta-molybdates.

The curve II in the figure, which is more or less straight, shows the susceptibility values calculated on the basis of mixture law.